

Bionic Smartwatch Application

The Bionic Smartwatch application is used as a control interface to the Bionic AI Chip and acts as a sensor that measures heartrate and step count of the person wearing the app.

Additionally Warning messages can be displayed in the following cases:

- The system is not assembled properly
- A part of the system is not working properly
- The BSN has hardware issues that need to be reported
- The user is in a critical posture and should change it

The app can be downloaded on the Google Play Store:

<https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=de.dfki.av.mhs.peripheralwatch&gl=DE>

The following pages describe the different views in the app.

Screens descriptions

1. Start Screen: **Watch not connected to system**

2. Start Screen - **Watch connected to system**

3. Settings: Click on settings button on the first screen to change the settings.

4. Notifications enabled: As soon as the watch is connected to the system and the characteristics are enabled, the application is redirected to the second screen. If the system is not Running yet, the right button will be gray as measurements are not yet enabled and pressing the right button does not have any effect. The current status of the system will be displayed above the buttons.

5. System Running: On Measurement Start from the web UI or the Bionic Edge App, the right button will get green and the status will change to RUNNING.
- a. **Not fully Connected**, left red button (Info) denotes some disconnection in the system.

- b. System Running: **Fully Connected**, Green left button (Info) denotes everything is connected.

6. System not fully connected: When everything is not connected, and you click on info button from previous screen OFF(Red) means **not connected**.

e.g., HUB is **connected** but, RIGHT-upper body part is **not connected**.

Info Screen- System fully connected: When everything is connected, and you click on info button from previous screen, all buttons will be green means that system is well connected.

7. System Paused: On Second screen, Right Red button (red) denotes system is in Pause state.

8. Settings screen: To change the settings, **swipe-down** to open **settings** screen.

9. Warning: When there is warning from system!!

How to Update the Application

Make sure that the Smartwatch is connected to the Smartphone and that the Smartphone is connected to internet.

- 1- Open the Playstore in the smartwatch by clicking in the side left button
- 2- Click on the Search icon on the top screen

- 3- Select the Keyboard icon on the right side of the screen

- 4- Use the keyboard to write **BIONIC** and click again the search icon

- 5- The application called Bionic Smartwatch will appear, select it and if there is a new version available in the play store, the Update button will appear, click on it to have the latest version of the Bionic Smartwatch in your smartwatch.

